

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE INNOVATION COMPETENCE STRUCTURE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract. *The article provides information about innovative education, which provides quality changes in the activity of the object and subject, is widely popular and has high efficiency. Also, issues such as types of pedagogical innovations related to individual pedagogical activities, types of pedagogical innovations related to the methodical association of pedagogues, types of pedagogical innovations according to their socio-pedagogical significance, and types of pedagogical innovations according to the scale of innovative activities are covered.*

Keywords: *education and training, innovation, pedagogical innovation, mastering, training and learning, modified innovation, integrated innovation, educational goal.*

It is known that in the process of globalization, a number of scientific researches are being carried out to ensure the harmony of models of continuous professional development of pedagogical personnel, to improve the pedagogical and psychological mechanisms of developing the innovative potential of pedagogical personnel in the process of professional development. Due to the conflict between the need for rapid development of the educational process and the lack of readiness of pedagogical personnel to implement it, pedagogical innovations have become educational tools, the need for new knowledge has increased as a result of the popularization of the introduction of innovations, and today in pedagogy "innovation", "innovation", "pedagogical" such concepts as "innovation" are widely used. After all, as President Shavkat Mirziyoev said, "Innovation is the future. If we start building our great future today, we should start it on the basis of innovative ideas and an innovative approach [1].

The concept of "innovation" is derived from the Latin language (in-to, novus-new), which means "renewal", "mastery", "introducing something new", "introducing something new", "introducing something new". In turn, the word "new" is the main core of this concept.

Various definitions of this concept have been formulated to date, and based on their analysis, we felt the need to determine our research direction.

According to S.Turgunov, a pedagogue scientist who created a unique school of educational system management, innovation is a goal-oriented change that brings new, is to introduce relatively stable elements, innovations that are inextricably linked with the spiritual and cultural relations of the people and the socio-economic development of the country in general [2].

According to M.Jumaniyozova, if the activity is short-term, does not have the characteristics of an integrated system, and has set itself the task of changing only some components of a specific system, then we call it "innovation". we will be thinking about. If the activity is carried out on the basis of a certain conceptual approach, if its result leads to the development of that system or its fundamental change, we can call it "innovation".

In terms of activity, innovation is limited in scope and time, and innovation is holistic and continuous. As a result of innovation, individual elements in the current system are changed, and as a result of innovation, the positions of the subjects of practice are completely renewed, the relations in the system and the system are reformed [3].

According to D.Yunusova, who fundamentally researched the theory and practice of preparing a future mathematics teacher for innovative activities, defined the concept of "innovation" as "a goal-oriented change, the transfer of a system in the field of application from one state to a qualitatively new state, radically improve it" [4].

Although each of the above definitions has its own content, there is a need to develop an improved definition of this concept. Based on this basis, we created the following generalized definition of the concept of "innovation": "Innovation is a quality change in the activity of the object and subject, which is widely popular and has high efficiency, conventionality and is to introduce innovation in a systematic, organic and continuous manner, acting as a "bridge" between perspectives. Pedagogical innovations are of particular importance among various types of innovations, and are considered an important means of professional training of future teachers.

Pedagogical innovation means learning, mastering, evaluating, using and implementing pedagogical innovations. In turn, there are several types of pedagogical innovations: modified, corrective, changing, local, modular, systematic, etc. However, a more generalized classification of pedagogical innovations reflects the following view:

- 1) innovations related to the goals and objectives and content of education and training;
- 2) innovations in the methods, methodology and technology of the educational process;
- 3) innovations in the organization of the educational process.

Pedagogical innovations are broad in scope and do not have a clear typology or classification that is universally accepted. There are more than twenty classifications for the grouping of innovations, for example: long-term innovations and short-term innovations, radical and reformist, authoritarian and liberal, initiative and administrative, etc.

According to the characteristics of innovations, they can be classified differently on different bases, that is, today there is no complete classification of innovation. At the same time, according to the information found in the framework of our research, in the organization of pedagogical processes and ensuring their effectiveness, first of all, it is appropriate to take into account which link of the pedagogical processes the news belongs to [5].

Based on the above-mentioned classifications of pedagogical innovations, the classification of B.Khodzhaev and Sh. Zufarov [6] it is possible to create the following generalized system of pedagogical innovations that can be used in pedagogical education processes:

1. In connection with the deepening of production relations, innovations can be distinguished into the following types:

1) modified innovations. For example, "electronic group magazines", "electronic dean's office";

corrective innovation. For example, the "revised Rating Regulation";

1) transformative innovations. For example, "Internet education";

2) integrated innovation. For example, "person-oriented distance learning technologies";

2. Pedagogical innovations can be divided into the following groups according to their relationship to the components of the educational process:

1) pedagogical innovations related to educational goals and objectives. For example, "turning the identified educational goals into educational tasks";

2) innovations related to the content of education and upbringing. For example, "integration and differentiation of educational content", "information and forecasting";

3) innovations related to forms, methods, tools and technologies of education. For example, non-traditional forms of lessons, interactive methods, multimedia tools, effective educational technologies (modular educational technologies, cultural-humanitarian approach technologies);

4) innovations related to diagnosis of education. For example, educational portfolios;

3. Pedagogical innovations are divided into the following groups according to the attitude of educational subjects to personality formation:

1) innovations related to the development of certain abilities of pedagogic personnel. For example, the development of joint cooperation activities;

2) innovations related to the development of PW, activity methods and competence of pedagogues and students.

4. According to the field of pedagogical application, pedagogical innovations are divided into the following types:

1) pedagogical innovations used in the educational process. For example, information technologies of education;

2) pedagogical innovations used in the training course. For example, an electronic map;

3) pedagogical innovations used in the field of education. For example, democratization of education;

4) innovations used in the field of educational management. For example, the transition of education from state management to state-public management.

5. According to the type of interaction of the participants of the pedagogical process, pedagogical innovations are divided into the following groups: 1) innovations related to team teaching; 2) innovations in group teaching; 3) facilitation; 4) tutoring.

6. According to their functional capabilities, pedagogical innovations are divided into the following types:

1) innovations related to the conditions (ensures a change in the educational environment, socio-cultural conditions, etc.);

2) innovations in the form of products (pedagogical tools, projects, technologies).

3) introduction of management news.

7. According to the methods of implementation, pedagogical innovations are divided into the following types:

1) planned pedagogical innovations;

2) systematic pedagogical innovations;

3) periodical pedagogical innovations;

4) spontaneous pedagogical innovations;

5) accidental pedagogical innovations;

6) spontaneous pedagogical innovations.

8. Pedagogical innovations are divided into the following types according to their spatial orientation:

1) pedagogical innovations related to the activities of individual pedagogues;

- 2) pedagogical innovations related to the methodical association of pedagogues;
- 3) innovations related to the activity of a separate educational institution;
- 4) pedagogical innovations at the district, city, region, republic level;
- 5) international pedagogical innovations.

9. Pedagogical innovations are divided into the following types according to their socio-pedagogical importance:

- 1) pedagogical innovations in special educational institutions;
- 2) pedagogical innovations specific to pedagogues of a specific professional-typological group.

10. According to the scale of innovative activities, pedagogical innovations are divided into the following types: local; public; global.

M.V.Klarin distinguishes two types of innovative approach to education: 1) modernized innovations aimed at obtaining guaranteed results within the framework of the traditional reproductive orientation of the educational process; 2) transformed innovations aimed at reorganizing the traditional educational process. The scientist calls the first approach a technological approach, and the second a research approach.

O.G.Khomeriki distinguishes the following types of innovations in connection with one or another component of the educational process:

- 1) innovations in educational content;
- 2) innovations in the methods, methodology and technology of the educational process;
- 3) innovations in the organization of the educational process;
- 4) innovations in the management of the educational system.

It is clear from the above classifications of pedagogical innovations that innovations in the educational system are:

- purpose, content, method and technology, form of educational organization, management system;

- method of organizing pedagogical activity and learning process;

- system of control and evaluation of the level of education;

- education financing system;

- educational and methodological support;

- system of educational work;

- curriculum and educational programs;

- occurs in connection with changes in the activities of professors and students, educators and learners.

Agreeing with the above views of scientists, we came to the conclusion that one of the manifestations of innovations in education is the formation of a person who fully reflects human potential.

Based on the theoretical analysis of revealing the nature of innovative potential of pedagogic personnel, it can be noted that this problem is very complex and multi-faceted, and requires further research. In particular, in addition to researching the theoretical foundations of the innovative activity of pedagogic personnel, there is a special need to research the andrapedagogical conditions for the implementation of the innovative potential of pedagogic personnel in the pedagogical activity through external influence in the process of independent professional development.

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